

Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication

For Policymakers

Trust

Framing and Sensemaking

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Collaboration

Pre-Crisis

Imminent Crisis

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Introduction

The **Crisis Navigator** is designed as a **strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who communicate science in times of crises**. Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a **sensitising tool** – a conceptual and practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work. In this case, the guiding question is: **What are crucial considerations for policymakers who need to communicate about science when a crisis emerges?**

The present tool is targeted towards **policymakers** within governmental or regulatory institutions who are responsible for developing, implementing, and evaluating crisis responses and policies that shape public action. In doing so, **they also act as science communicators, translating technical evidence into accessible guidance, framing risks for the public, and signaling the rationale behind policy choices**. The many challenges they face include time pressure, incomplete or evolving evidence, conflicting stakeholder interests, and the need to maintain public trust while ensuring effective crisis management.

The Crisis Navigator is structured along four stages: pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis, taking into account the **evolving dynamics of a crisis**. Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as a **guide for policymakers to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis**, supporting them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

Challenge: Complexity and uncertainty

GUIDING QUESTION

What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer the guiding question, consider:

Information gaps: Policymakers should identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise in understanding the situation before, during, and after communicating. When a crisis is imminent, misinformation tends to spread rapidly as uncertainty grows and people may seek explanations or reassurance. Rumors, speculation, and emotionally charged content often fill information gaps before verified facts are available. In such situations, policymakers should communicate early, clearly, and consistently, providing verified information through trusted channels and acknowledging what is still unknown.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Policymakers should aim to integrate multiple perspectives in response to these questions to offer a balanced and comprehensive understanding of an issue, while acknowledging limitations and areas of ongoing research or debate. Most importantly, engaging openly with experts, the media, and the public about these questions of expertise and evidence can help sustain trust and legitimacy, which are essential for collective action in times of crisis.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations.

Underlying conflicts

GUIDING QUESTION

What does each stakeholder need?

Underlying conflicts can stem from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. They can exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. By adopting inclusive, transparent, and participatory approaches that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?,” policymakers who need to communicate about science can help to shed light on underlying conflicts, and generate more effective and sustainable solutions to urgent societal issues. Policymakers can address underlying conflicts by acknowledging divergent values and interests early on, rather than treating disagreement as misinformation or resistance. This involves creating inclusive and transparent deliberation spaces where affected groups can voice concerns and contribute to decisionmaking.

Trust

GUIDING QUESTION

How can policymakers enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

Science communication by policymakers during crises should prioritize building and maintaining trust. While trust is important throughout all crisis phases, participatory activities that foster trust, such as citizen dialogues, are difficult to organize during the actual or imminent crisis phase. Pre-crisis efforts should therefore include participatory platforms that support mutual understanding, involving not only the general public but also sustained engagement among policymakers, scientists, and (local) governments. These activities should emphasize transparency and inclusion. It can be challenging to balance being transparent about scientific uncertainty whilst remaining a credible source of knowledge. By acknowledging uncertainty, emotions, and the diverse contexts of those affected, trust can be strengthened. Addressing both trust and collaboration in the pre-crisis phase thus lays a strong foundation for effective science communication during crises..

Collaboration

GUIDING QUESTION

How can policymakers facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

To ensure a coordinated, efficient and effective response, collaboration is essential. Policymakers who communicate about science play a key role by enabling clear, consistent and credible communication that fosters trust and understanding. Involving scientists from various disciplines, (local) governments, civil society and other stakeholders (such as first responders or NGOs) already in the pre-crisis phase, helps establish interdisciplinary expert networks that can be rapidly mobilized when needed. Such collaboration reduces fragmented expertise and narrative gaps in science communication during crises. By bringing together scientists, policymakers, journalists, and practitioners, such collaboration fosters more coherent and context-sensitive messaging. However, differences in language and professional norms can hinder coordination, making trust-building and clear role allocation crucial.

Framing and sensemaking

GUIDING QUESTION

How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

Whereas framing refers to the way information is presented, sense-making is about how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a sender to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. Policymakers should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as mediator between stakeholders. Framing can significantly influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information; yet, this does not mean that through framing policymakers are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. The ways in which science is communicated can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties in an easy-to-understand way, and by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities.

Ethical issues

GUIDING QUESTION

How can policymakers promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Communicating about science can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows various stakeholders to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. It can also promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive dialogue, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing the diversity of cultural values and beliefs. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

Values and emotions

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do researchers engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are a key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. On the one hand, emotions are an important source of information about the values at stake in times of crises. On the other hand, giving space to emotions and values in communication can render it more effective because it enables connecting with audiences and spurs action. By connecting with values and emotions through interaction with general publics and civil society, trust and collaboration can also be upheld during crises.

Power

GUIDING QUESTION

Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

Crises require rapid decision-making to mobilize necessary stakeholders and processes, often leading to top-down policy approaches that limit bottom-up decision making and overlook valuable knowledge of stakeholders such as local residents or civil society. Policymakers communicating about science during crises should therefore be aware of power dynamics. Here, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders. Key questions include who holds power and responsibility, who shapes public discourse, what knowledge is shared, and whose knowledge is ignored. Recognizing and navigating these power dynamics is crucial for ethical and effective communication of science in policy contexts that promotes informed decision-making, equity and public trust.

Reflective practice

GUIDING QUESTION

How can policymakers continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

It is helpful for policymakers to regularly self-reflect on their science communication activities during any of the crisis stages. Reflective practice means adopting a critical and reflective stance to responses in specific situations, and to understand how these responses are shaped by frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. This can help to become sensitive to one's own position and assumptions when it comes to tensions and underlying conflicts that may be exacerbated in times of crises. Insights gained from this reflection can help strengthen strategies in future crises.

Trust & Collaborations

GUIDING QUESTION

How can policymakers build trust and facilitate constructive exchanges?

Similar to the pre- and imminent crisis phases, it is essential to build both trust and collaboration during the post-crisis phase; and it is crucial to repair and restore trust where it was lost or damaged. This is probably the best way to ensure rapid mobilization and effective science communication during possible future crises. It is helpful here to compare and contrast policymaking approaches in other crisis contexts, paying attention not only to visible manifestations of a communication crisis (e.g., misinformation, disinformation), but also to structural factors (e.g., inequitable access to information) and cultural factors (e.g., symbolic framings, such as "ignorant publics") that may or may not be used to justify structural exclusions.

Deliverable 2.1 Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

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